

A STUDY OF CONFLICT MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS OF EXECUTIVES & BLUE-COLLAR WORKERS IN AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MAHARASHTRA STATE.

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ABSTRACT:

Purpose - The purpose of this article is to elucidate the influence that studying Conflict Management Systems of executives and blue-collar workers Job Satisfaction and socioeconomic impacts can be achieved in Automobile Industry through conflict management learning.

Findings - Application of Conflict Management learning helps to improve individual and group perception of control and conflict management systems.

Limitations/implications - The article is focused on recent trends in Conflict Management Systems in order to involve the participants into a realistic Automobile business management experience.

Practical Implications - Results encourage the incorporation of these Conflict Management Systems into educational programs related to Societal Impact. Conflict Management learning improves conflict management within and between groups, especially in the complementary activities and negotiations with real agents; it also fosters motivation and cooperative attitudes.

Value - This article contributes to increase knowledge in conflict management for Individual and workgroups maintaining intensive and relentless relationships over a relatively long period of time. At a more practical level, experience on conflict management generates acceptance of the conflict as a part of the decision making process, which improves the entrepreneurial attitude for all participants resulting in Job Satisfaction and Socioeconomic impacts.

KEYWORDS: Conflict Management, Learning, Socioeconomic impact, Executives, Blue-Collar workers, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Performance

1. INTRODUCTION:

Conflict is natural and necessary part of our lives. Whether at home with our families, at work with colleagues or in negotiations between

governments, conflict pervades our relationships. The paradox of conflict is that it is both the force that can tear relationships apart and the force that binds them together. This dual nature of conflict makes it an important concept to study and understand. Conflict is an inevitable and necessary feature of domestic and international relations. The challenge facing governments is not the elimination of conflict, but rather, how to effectively address conflict when it arises. While most government officials in Africa are not frequently confronted by large-scale violence or humanitarian crises, they are often involved in lesser but nevertheless serious conflicts over trade, refugees, borders, water, defence, etc. Their government may be party to the conflict or called on to serve as mediator. In either case, they require particular skills and techniques to tackle the issues in a constructive fashion. Conflict can be managed negatively through avoidance at one extreme and the use or threat of force at the other. Alternatively, conflict can be managed positively through negotiation, joint problem-solving and consensus-building. These options help build and sustain constructive bilateral and multi-lateral relations.

Constructive conflict management is as much a science as an art. It is based on a substantial body of theory, skills and techniques developed from decades of experience in international peacekeeping, peacemaking and peacebuilding. Acquiring a better understanding of the conceptual tools and skills professional conflict managers use can help us gain confidence in addressing conflict in a manner which resolves the issues and

maintains or even strengthens relationships. While we may not all go on to become professional peacemakers, these skills and knowledge can help us in any social setting. These tools can help for example, government officials, address disputes more quickly and effectively, preventing them from growing into domestic or international crises.

2. BACKGROUND OF STUDY:

Strikes, lockouts, tool downs are recurrently happening in Organizations. At some point of time, High level of conflict resulted in human loss. Examples: Violence at Maruti Suzuki India Limited, Manesar Plant, Haryana. Awanish Kumar Dev, General Manager-HR, burned to death as violent mob of workers set on fire his office in company in the month of July 2012. In Maharashtra strike was happened in Bajaj Auto Limited, Chakan Plant, Pune. Mahindra & Mahindra faced strikes, tool downs in Nashik & Igatpuri plants respectively. Recently strike and hunger strike happened in Force Motors Limited, Pune plant from the month of March, 2015 to October 2015. These episodes indicate lack of effective Conflict Management Systems in organizations which in turn affecting organizational performance and sustainable growth with regard to productivity, profitability, sales, socioeconomic aspects, Job satisfaction and human capital.

Labour issues have been a regular pain for Maruti, which had seen a major unrest at its Manesar plant in 2012 that also resulted in the death of a senior HR manager. The company has been trying to sensitize managerial and other staff on issues related to worker management. Also, it has cut the dependence on casual workers to stem the unrest. Maruti Suzuki was paying Rs.7000 per month to contract workers and Rs.25000 per month to Permanent workers at Maruti Suzuki India Limited, Manesar plant which was the main reason for violence in July, 2012.

Tata Motors Limited Sacking of white collar employees:

According to The Times of India report, Thursday dated, May 25, 2017 entitled "Tata Motors axes up to 1,500 managers" illustrates White Collar employees suffering due to automation and organizational restructuring.

Tata Motors said it has reduced its managerial workforce by up to 1,500 people domestically as part of an organizational restructuring exercise. "The reference (total managers) on which we started (the exercise) was in the vicinity of 13000...we do see as far as the white collar population is concerned, an overall reduction in the vicinity of 10-12 % (up to 1,500)," MD & CEO Guenter Butschek said.

The company joins a growing number of organizations adopting such strategies for a variety of reasons, ranging from cutting the flab to automation. These job cuts, which have led to concerns on 'jobless economic growth' in various quarters, have been across multiple sectors, including capital goods, banking & finance, and information technology.

The Tata Motors management, however, said blue collar or worker jobs have not been impacted as part of exercise.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the impact of conflict on Organizational Performance with respect to Executives and Blue-Collar workers workforce size.
2. To study the impact of conflict on Organizational Performance with respect to companies paid up capital.
3. To study the present conflict management systems with reference to executives and blue-collar workers in Automobile Industry.
4. To study Executives satisfaction in the present conflict management system.
5. To study Blue-Collar workers satisfaction in the present conflict management system.
6. To suggest sound/effective conflict management system in automobile industry.
7. To study the consequences of high level of conflict on societal level.

4. THEORETICAL REVIEW:

4.1 The 3 Rs - Respect, Recognition, Relatedness - Essentials in Conflict Resolution:

Recent brain research has proven scientifically what many religions and cultures have known over centuries, and what a team of innovation catalysts in the USA discovered in the late

1950s: Treating people with respect not only benefits our relationships - it also helps us to resolve conflicts by creating a positive, collaborative climate while we work together to develop creative solutions to problems.

Neuroscience research, well summarised in David Rock's SCARF model (2008), also shows why the "positive behaviours" demonstrating respect, recognition and relatedness promote mutual understanding, reduce stress levels, enable the brain to function well - and to enable people to develop shared and implementable solutions to sticky problems.

Particularly when seeking to resolve conflicts, the ability to create a climate of trust and collaboration is important. At the same time, the ability to develop a variety of possible, creative options from which parties to the conflict can choose, and hopefully achieve consensus rather than mere compromise, can be invaluable. (Nolan, 2004)

Underlying the ability to create a positive climate are three important elements - which are The Three R's - Respect, Recognition and Relatedness. These three are closely related and reinforce one another. They also resonate with the traditional African Ubuntu culture.

4.2 Remembrance, atonement, reconciliation and forgiveness is the way to go in conflict resolution, writes JOHN MOOLAKKATTU:

The power of forgiveness as a means of conflict resolution or transformation was emphasized by thinkers like Hannah Arendt as it allows human beings to come to terms with their undesirable past, thereby changing the rule that governs the power relationship between the former victimiser and his victim. The application of ideas and beliefs that are relevant in the personal and religious realm into politics is however a project that many political realists would find difficult to agree. Forgiveness, in short, seems to represent the personal, the private, the spiritual.

It is the encouraging results from the experience of the South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission and the revival of the Christian idea of forgiveness that also finds reflection in most religions in one form or the other, which made the concept popular in recent

years. Some even see this as a sort of opportunity for national self-reflexivity and social healing.

4.3 Skills Development for Conflict Transformation:

We can achieve conflict transformation through the following ways:

1. **Negotiation:** Negotiation is a voluntary attempt to resolve conflicts that arise from competing needs, interests and goals. It is a problem solving approach in which parties seek agreement rather than resort to violence and force. In situations where relationships are threatened or have been harmed, high mistrust exists and violence has occurred, negotiation as a problem solving approach is particularly difficult but all the more relevant.

2. **Communication:** One of the deepest needs of all human beings is to feel understood and be accepted by others. Offering understanding to another person is a potent form of empowerment. We need not agree with others to empower them in this way; we need only to make it clear through our eyes, body posture and tone of voice that we want to see the world from their perspective. Our interactions with others must come from a point of deep, non-judgmental interest. The key is to grasp the why behind what is being said or done in order to gain insight into the deeper interests and needs of the person with whom we are communicating. From the moment that people feel you are truly seeking to understand, they begin dealing with problems and other people more constructively. Good listening skills are used throughout any process designed to constructively resolve conflict. Good listening is, perhaps, the most significant skill a mediator or facilitator brings to assist parties in conflict.

3. **Mediation:** Mediation refers to a process through which a third party provides procedural assistance to help individuals or groups in conflict to resolve their differences. Mediation processes vary throughout the world in form and underlying philosophy. In many Western countries, the mediator is usually an independent, impartial person who

has no decision-making authority. In other societies, it may be more important that the mediator is known and trusted by the parties to the conflict rather than being seen as impartial.

4.4 The Art of Thinking Clearly:

In Conflict Management making right decisions at the right time with right thinking are very important to avoid any high level of conflict or major conflict between management and Employees. Employees include executives and blue-collar workers. In short Conflict Management means making right decisions to avoid major conflicts between management and employees.

Self-help author, Switzerland's Rolf Dobelli talks to REENA SINGH about the cognitive biases that play havoc with our decision-making skills. Rolf Dobell's *The Art of Thinking Clearly* has sold over a million copies, topping bestseller charts across the world since it was first published in 2013. The book's back blurb is eye-catching – it asks whether you have ever invested time in something that with hindsight, just wasn't worth it or whether you have ever continued doing something you knew was bad for you. It asks another question – have you ever taken credit for success, but blamed failure on external circumstances? 'Yes, you do that all the time,' I heard a disapproving voice tell me deep inside my head even as I was reading the first question. The voice got consistently louder with more questions that followed.

5. THE PROPOSED CONFLICT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM:

People as vital elements of cultural change, are the key to successful implementation of TQM in any organization. Human Resource & IR Managers must play a central part in this change process. They can offer advice on how to create empowerment and teamwork. They should introduce and continually improve TQM Philosophy based processes in Conflict management systems to enable creation of high performance based work system. In conclusion, if an excellence based culture is to be implemented and sustained the TQM

Philosophy will continue to play a vital role. The 14 points of Dr.W.Edwards Deming form a framework for the implementation of TQM. Organizations must learn to devise and administer conflict management systems based on TQM Philosophy so that they fit into a larger IR & HR strategy, where they can play an important part in the change management process.

6. ANALYSIS & FINDINGS:

I have selected total 13 companies for survey which includes 9 Automobile companies and 4 Auto ancillary companies. 66 Executives and 280 Blue-Collar workers responded to questionnaires sent. One way ANOVA is used for testing of data.

Major findings are mentioned below:

1. Executives are satisfied with present conflict management system in their company.
2. Blue-Collar workers are not satisfied with present conflict management system in their company.
3. Sufferings of Blue-Collar workers are more as compared to executives.

7. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS:

☑ The dispute resolution processes in place are many and varied. There is clearly no one best way. What seems to be occurring is a lot of experimentation.

☑ Narrowing the gap between HRM and IR. This requires changes in the thinking of unions and managements.

☑ For the most part, organizations do not broadly communicate information about their conflict resolution process. There is a strong reliance on managers and supervisors, HR, or the 'culture' of the organization to make employees aware that there is a process available.

☑ Organizations must learn to devise and administer conflict management systems based on TQM Philosophy so that they fit into a larger IR & HR strategy.

☑ Little tracking and few statistics are kept on use of the process or types of issues that arise. While formal and informal processes exist in organizations, they do not seem to be used

frequently. There is a general sense that group conflicts decreased and individual conflicts increased in recent years.

☒ The HR and IR department usually is responsible for the design and implementation of the conflict resolution process. HR plays a facilitating role, generally acting as consultant to both employees and management. Line management or operations are typically responsible for use of the process or for ensuring that policies are in place and followed.

☒ The Changes in Industrial Relations Practices to be incorporated to have an Effective Conflict Management System.

☒ Integration of Industrial relations and Human Resource Management is essential to devise effective conflict management system.

☒ Training & Development on conflict resolution is minimal in most organizations, although managers and supervisors may receive such training indirectly as part of management development or first-line supervision training. Conflict management or dispute resolution skills are not clearly identified as a core competency.

☒ Sound/Effective Conflict Management System needs to be developed as per organizational requirements to avoid destructive or high level of conflict to achieve socioeconomic impacts and better organizational performance.

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